

Particle Detectives

Experiment Guide

Author: Michael Gregory

1. Air Vortex

Inspiration

Dave Haller - Eureka, California, USA (homemade vortex cannon)

Anja Horvat - CERN (Seeing the Invisible)

Bryson Gore - Royal Institute, England (bubbles to visualise vortex)

Scientific Concepts

Air is made of particles that are invisible to the human eye.

Materials

- Empty cardboard box
 - e.g. from A3 paper, approx. dimensions 42 x 32 x 25 cm, like this:
<https://www.amazon.co.uk/Everyday-EVERYDAY80A3BOX-Paper-Pack-Reams>
- Garbage bag (e.g. 20 L)
- Packing tape
- Several small bubble wands /containers (at least 8 pieces).
 - E.g., <https://www.amazon.fr/dp/B07BYTSQMJ>.
- Scissors / utility knife
- Paper cup/toilet paper roll etc. as a target

Assembly/Preparation

The goal is to have a box which is open at one end, and has a hole of approx. 10-15 cm at the other end.

1. Cut one side of the box open (remove the whole side). Depending on the box you find, how you do this might vary. (see example below)
2. Cut a circular hole (10-15 cm) in the centre of the opposite side of the box (see image above).
3. Fold and cut a garbage bag to cover the one end, with a few cm to spare to tape securely. Depending on the thickness of the bag, 2 folds is usually good. A thinner bag with fewer folds will last only one or two shows. If you want it to last longer, you can reinforce the bag with extra tape.
4. Pull the bag fairly tightly over the open end of the box. Tape, staple, and/or use elastics to hold the bag in place. The bag will tend to loosen with use, so it's a good idea to start a bit tight.

Hitting the bag with an open hand should produce an air vortex out of the hole. As this will be invisible, it's handy to have a second person to feel the vortex for testing. Otherwise use anything light, like paper, toilet paper, plastic cups, curtains, etc.

Air Vortex Cannon at ProNRG Science Festival, Kazakhstan
Photo by Nasko Stamenov

Experiment

A. Fixed target

1. Call three volunteers with long hair onto the stage. Arrange the volunteers at an angle so that (1) the audience can see their backs (and hair) and (2) you can use their hair as a target for your vortex cannon.
2. Aim vortices at the different volunteer's hair. The audience should be able to correctly identify which target was hit by the vortex.

B. Tracking

1. Give bubble solution & wands to several individuals in the audience. Make sure to choose individuals that are within a reasonably compact area near the front. If there is an aisleway, it works well to have the people next to the aisle blow bubbles to fill the aisle.
2. Demonstrate blowing bubbles with the wands and then ask the audience to start blowing bubbles. Note: It can be surprising how long this takes, especially for adults. Be ready to help open the bubble solution.
3. From nearby, start aiming vortices through bubbles. It should be possible to see the traces of where each vortex travels!

What's Going On?

When you push the garbage bag, it pushes the air in the box forward. When the moving air encounters the hole at the other end of the box, the air in the centre is able to exit the box more freely, creating a zone of higher speed and lower pressure. At the edge of the hole,

the air will slow down. Together, this creates a ring vortex which can travel across the room.

When an air vortex encounters a fixed target, e.g., a volunteer with long hair, the vortex deposits all its energy. Via this interaction, we can tell the position and the energy of the vortex, but in detecting it the vortex is destroyed. This is analogous to a particle being absorbed by a calorimeter in particle detectors. A calorimeter can give a lot of information about the particle, however the particle is destroyed in the process.

By contrast, the air vortex moving through an audience full of bubbles is analogous to a particle moving through a tracker. The vortex is only interacting weakly, and largely continuing its path unaffected by interaction with the tracker.

Troubleshooting

- **Vortices are not good enough:** The most common issue is the garbage bag being too tight or too loose. The solution is to reattach the bag with a different tension until it works well.
- **The bag is well secured, but it still doesn't work:** try changing the size of the hole. Generally, a smaller hole will give a smaller vortex, but the smaller vortex will tend to be more concentrated. Box geometry and hole size also play a role. In general, smaller holes will create smaller vortices which can be more concentrated in energy. There is a balance between intensity and size, but when in doubt, try a smaller size hole to increase the intensity of the vortex.

My example:

The most common dimensions I have successfully used are:

- Box: 42 x 32 x 25 cm (this is the size of a 5-pack of A3 paper, found commonly in photocopy rooms of schools and offices)
 - For an A3 paper box, you can cut the whole side and the hole hole from the opposite more square ends, and when available use a second lid on the bottom for support.
- Hole: 12 cm diameter
- See Dave Haller teach me this experiment in 2017:
<https://youtu.be/er7dcVrBxRE?si=ET19X58X1Zq2S5b9&t=70>

2. Beer Bottle Gas Thermometer

Scientific Concepts

Thermometers – function and use

Heat/Thermal Expansion

Can be extended to include: calibration, ideal gas laws, absolute zero

Materials

- Empty **glass** bottle (beer, wine, juice, etc.)
- One-hole stopper of suitable diameter for bottle*
- Thin diameter transparent tubing**
- Balloon
- Coloured Water

Assembly

1. Insert tubing into the stopper, allowing one or two cm of extra length below the bottom of the stopper. (Do this step before the show to save time.)
2. Insert balloon into top of bottle, and carefully fill with coloured water (the balloon should not completely cover the opening before it is full, or else the pressure of the air inside the bottle will prevent the balloon from filling).
3. Once the balloon is full, insert a stopper into the bottle. Normally, once a seal has been formed, the stopper will displace its own volume of water up the tube, and so your starting temperature should have a few cm of water visible above your stopper.

The thermometer should now be ready to use to demonstrate changes in temperature.

Experiment

You can do this experiment either yourself or with the help of a volunteer. Tightly hold the bottle with both hands, covering as much surface as possible. The heat from the hands should be enough to make the water rise 10-20 cm.

What's Going On?

Air is a gas made of up various molecules which are moving with energies proportional to the temperature. As the temperature increases, the molecules move faster, which causes an increase in either pressure, volume, or both. As long as the height of the water in the

tube is fairly small, we assume that the thermometer is operating under constant pressure (1% increase per 10cm height of water), and so the increase in volume will be directly proportional to the increase in temperature.

Troubleshooting

- **Leaking water:** The most common problem with this type of thermometer is an improper seal between the tube and the stopper. Usually this will become apparent with leaking water. When this occurs, the level of water in the tube will drop, often slowly, at constant temperature. It may still be possible to demonstrate a rise and fall with large changes in temperature, however a leaky seal will make any meaningful calibration impossible. Generally, the tighter the fit between the stopper and the tube, the better the seal. This is easiest with thick-walled, semi-rigid tubing and a rubber or cork stopper.

My example

- Outside of a lab, a one-hole stopper can be hard to find. Homemade alternatives are possible using a wine cork, oil dispenser, bottle cap, etc., but take care to make a tight seal.
- Bathroom caulking and plumbers' tape can be useful for sealing.
- Assemble and test ahead of time to avoid a useless mess on stage.
- For tubing, you could also use a transparent straw, glass tube, or combination thereof.

My all-time favourite set-up is:

- glass tubing in stopper, sticking out a few cm (tubing about 5 cm length, 6 mm diameter)
- plastic tubing (a few cm long, 6 mm inner diameter), to connect glass tubing to straw
- transparent drinking straw on top

But, unless you already have glass tubing cut to length and smoothed, it's not worth sourcing and preparing all this, it's easier use to use some tubing.

Beer-bottle thermometer at Ho International School, Ghana
(photo by Christoffer Akpeloo)

Going Further

Calibration

The thermometer can be calibrated by placing it in two water baths of different known temperatures. Within reasonable uncertainty, the thermometer can be considered to operate at constant pressure, and therefore increase in volume is proportional to increase in temperature, and a linear scale can be used to both interpolate and extrapolate between the known temperatures. (Ex. if at 20°C the height is 2 cm, and at 30°C the height is 7 cm, the thermometer is expected to move 0.5cm per °C. Interpolating, 22°C can be marked at 3cm, 24°C at 4cm, etc. Extrapolating, 40°C can be marked at 12 cm, 70°C at 27cm, etc. This can also be expressed as a linear equation: $h=0.5T-8$)

Calculating Absolute Zero

This simple gas thermometer can be used for a rough experimental measure of absolute zero, by extrapolating the calibration until the volume of gas in the bottle is zero. To do so, the height of water in the tube should be converted into volume, so we can extrapolate for the temperature at which the volume of the gas in the bottle should be zero.

This can be done graphically or algebraically, depending on the learning outcomes of this calculation.

For example, we continue the calibration example above, with height given by $h=0.5T-8$, then take into account the tube diameter of 4 mm and bottle volume of 750 mL. Modeling the tubing as a cylinder, we can find a volume of 0.126 mL per cm height ($V=\pi*r^2*h$). Comparison of the balloon's volume compared to the normal fill capacity of the bottle can lead to a more accurate starting volume, but if we assume the bottle to contain 750 mL of air, we can write $V=0.126h+750$

Useful Links

Beer bottle thermometer at ScienceMe Festival/Competition, Geneva, July 2022:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PO0DdyMhg3c>

Beer bottle thermometer in Spanish at DDD conference, Sevilla, Nov 2019:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GTekxAWYdrU>

Described in Science in School:

<https://www.scienceinschool.org/article/2022/my-favourite-experiments/>

3. Straw Trick for Static Electricity

Inspiration

Alex Pollack - former student in Paris, France

Scientific Concepts

Static electricity

Electrostatic induction

Triboelectric series

Materials

- 2 Plastic drinking straw
- Empty plastic bottle (Water, Coke, etc.)
- Paper (ex., A4, toilet paper, etc.)

Assembly

1. Rub both straws vigorously on paper. They will become charged.
2. Place one straw on top of the bottle.
3. Ask the audience to predict what will happen when the other is brought near (attraction, repulsion, or nothing.)
4. Bring the charged end of the straws together to demonstrate repulsion of like charges. (The straw on the bottle should spin away from the one in your hand.)
5. Repeat by bringing the paper near the straw. The paper will have an opposite charge, and will attract the straw.

6. Repeat with your own hand. (Audience will usually predict that nothing will happen, and be surprised to observe attraction - due to induction.)
7. Repeat with other objects, including volunteers, if you want to see how attractive they are!

What's Going On?

Triboelectric charging occurs when two different materials come in and out of contact (rubbing is the easiest, but not the only way to do this. See: <https://youtu.be/G3OaLFKy7E8?>)

The straws usually gain electrons from the paper. However, the experiment works exactly the same whether electrons are gained or lost. (There are very few experiments which could be done on stage or in a school to distinguish a positive vs. negative charge - most experiments are simply relative to a known test charge.) Regardless of charge sign, both straws will have the same charge, which will be opposite to the charge on the paper.

The straw is lightweight, and encounters little friction on top of a bottle cap. So even with a small charge, the straw should be able to move easily. (Both the straw and most bottle caps are curved, which makes it easy for the straw to roll off, but also makes it so there is very little resistance to motion.)

Similar charges repel, so the straws should repel each other. Opposite charges attract, so the straw should be attracted to the paper. A neutral object will have an opposite charge temporarily induced when brought near a charged object. This happens because electrons can move to maximize attraction. Indeed, electrons will move away from a negative charge and towards a positive charge. This happens in both conductors and insulators, and the observed effect will be quite similar, even though what happens at the atomic level will be very different

Troubleshooting

- **Little movement:** Humidity and other weather conditions can affect how well objects can gain and maintain charge; however a plastic straw is light enough and with little enough friction, this on its own should never create much of a problem for this experiment.
- **Straws are unavailable:** If straws are unavailable (in theory banned from sale in the EU and a number of other places), it is possible to use other materials, although it is hard to find a replacement that is as light, smooth, round and easily charged. However, if necessary, this experiment can work fine with ink cartridges from pens or a thin tube of paper, rolled up to the shape of a straw.
- **Different straws:** Some straws are made of different materials, and can actually pick up opposite charges! When using different straws, it is wise to test them ahead of time.

- **The straw does not move freely:** The straw should move very easily because of the low friction. Indeed, the round straw should have a small contact area with a rounded bottle cap. If either is less round, this can make the straw more stable (and fall off less often), but can significantly increase friction. If the straw doesn't move freely, check:
 - Bottle cap - should be slightly rounded (most are). Some brands/types may have a raised edge, which give two contact points, and significantly impedes motion.
 - Straw - especially when straws have travelled extensively in a backpack or bike bag, they may become less smooth. Try to keep at least one or two in good condition, and look for a good one before doing this experiment on stage. Don't forget that only one straw needs to sit on the bottle, and there is no problem using an old bent straw in your hand.

Deriving triboelectric series including human hair.
Virtual Science Camps: Electrostatics - A Spark of Inspiration

Going further

This experiment can easily be extended to a classroom activity to derive a whole triboelectric series using objects from around the room charged against each other, with the negative straw as a test charge. For an example of this, see:

<https://www.youtube.com/live/pJREo-d3ecQ?si=9YKyNpCZmbFeoTPi&t=1017>

Links:

- Video of Michael Gregory doing this in a storage closet at the Exploratorium:
<https://youtu.be/OMNU00hMXaY>

4. Coloured Fluorescence

Scientific Concepts

Fluorescence

Colour spectrum and energy levels

Materials

- RGB flashlight (e.g., <https://www.amazon.fr/gp/product/B08SBH6HJD/> or <https://www.amazon.fr/gp/product/B07TF6YNVL>).
- Fluorescent highlighters
- Paper

Note: This experiment must be done in a dark room. The darker the better. Still, it doesn't have to be pitch black as long as you have a strong enough light and use it close enough to the drawings.

Fluorescent Rainbow seen under red, blue and white light.

Assembly

1. Ask a few volunteers to make drawings using fluorescent highlighters, instructing one to use only a yellow highlighter. Ask them to sign their artwork with a non-fluorescent pen or pencil when they are finished.
2. When the drawings are ready, have volunteers take centre stage, ready for a dramatic unveiling. Make sure the room is dark and shine a bright red light on the volunteer who used yellow only and ask them to unveil their drawing.
3. The drawing should not appear, because the yellow highlighter only contains a phosphor, but no pigment, so will not interact with red light. The drawing should appear as a blank page, with the artist's signature on the bottom, as proof that it is indeed their drawing.
4. Depending on the mood, I'll tease the volunteer a lot, and pretend to give them a hard time for not having a drawing. They'll usually be confused, sometimes defensive, until I eventually turn on the blue light, and the yellow highlighter appears bright.

5. Fluorescence is the re-emission of light of a lower energy colour (ignoring double-photon fluorescence). Therefore the fluoresced light must have less energy than the incident light. So blue light has more energy than yellow, which has more energy than red.
6. Observe that yellow will fluoresce weakly under green light (it also blends in with green). This shows that yellow also has less energy than green light.
7. Next, show the multi-coloured drawings under red, blue and green light, to fit the remaining colours in the spectrum.

Troubleshooting

- **No RGB light source available:** This experiment can be done with other coloured light sources, however it's worth noticing that most coloured screens (ex. phones, computers) and most LED lights create their colours by varying the intensity of three primary coloured sources of light - red, green and blue, and so any thresholds for fluorescence will be due to the presence or absence of one of the primary colours in the mix. (This is generally not a concern with incandescent lights with colour filters, and less of a concern with fluorescent lights, whose phosphors generally won't be a simple combination of RGB.)
- **Room not dark enough:** If it is not possible to get the room adequately dark, this experiment can be done by blocking out most of the ambient light using a deep box, or other materials to create a locally dark area.

Going Further

For a classroom activity, chromatography can be used to separate phosphors and pigments from highlighters, and compared with chromatography of chlorophyll from leaves or salad, to isolate the red-fluorescence photocentre.

Links

Scientix TV (Ep. 8): <https://youtu.be/vGTDJiRMwJY?si=yfc5dSHpXi1C3Kqk&t=1044>

5. Household fluorescence

Inspiration

Nikola Karavasilev and Nasko Stamenov, Sofia, Bulgaria - highlighters in aqueous solution

Scientific Concepts

Fluorescence of everyday materials

Self-transparency of phosphors and scintillators

Materials

- UV flashlight (e.g., <https://www.amazon.fr/gp/product/B08J6GQF5S>)
- Olive oil
- Tonic water
- Fluorescent highlighter(s)
- Water bottle

Assembly

1. Fluorescent ink can be extracted by writing on a paper towel, moistening, and squeezing the ink into a bottle (or cup, etc.) of water. Drawing a roughly 5x5 cm square should give plenty of ink for a half litre bottle.
2. Shine UV light on different materials to demonstrate fluorescence.
 - a. **Olive oil** should fluoresce red/orange due to the red fluorescence of chlorophyll mixed with the green/yellow colour of the oil. Note that this is an example of self-opaque fluorescence - the green colour of the oil absorbs most of the fluoresced red light, so we cannot see the path, except for a few mm at the edge.
 - b. **Tonic water / highlighter solution**: it should be easy to see the path of the UV light through the solution. Quinine in the tonic water will fluoresce blue. Most highlighters are water-soluble, so their phosphors can be in solution. Notice that these are both examples of self-transparent fluorescence. This is a desired property when choosing materials for a scintillator - it should not absorb the photon which it is emitting.

Troubleshooting and Going Further

- **Olive oil does not fluoresce:** Not all olive oil will fluoresce well, particularly cheap oil which may have green dye added to give the appearance of chlorophyll. It's worth bringing a UV light to the store when shopping for olive oil, especially if you plan to use the oil on stage.
- **No access to tonic water:** The highlighter is a cheaper and more portable alternative to tonic water.
- **No access to UV light:** This is the only experiment in the show which uses UV light. If you don't already have one, it could be worth skipping the tonic water and olive oil, and simply using the highlighter solution with an RGB light.

6. Coloured Fire Tornado

Inspiration

Dave Haller - Eureka, California, USA - coloured flame tornado

Yerlan Uteilin - SonS Kazakhstan - "particle physics is boring - please include fire in show"

Scientific Concepts

Flame test (spectral colour of atoms)

Excitement of Electrons

Materials

- ethanol (70-80% solution. Methanol works better, but is more dangerous see "going further)
- white powder salts (salts marked with * are not ideal):
 - NaCl (sodium chloride, table salt - orange flame)
 - KCl (potassium chloride, sodium-free salt - lilac flame)
 - H₃BO₃ (boric acid, ant poison - green flame)
 - *LiCl (lithium chloride; it's strongly hygroscopic, so it absorbs water and becomes more of a white mess than a white powder; can also irritate your throat if you use a lot of it - red flame)
 - *CuCl₂ (copper chloride, blue-green powder; CuSO₄ is easier to get, but less soluble and harder to colour the flame - blue-green flame)
 - *CaCl₂ (calcium chloride; less soluble and harder to colour the flame - red flame)
- wire trash bin (e.g., <https://www.amazon.fr/gp/product/B003U6C4H>; any similar size should work. Larger than 24 cm in diameter might start being larger than the diameter of most standard frisbees/plates.)
- frisbee/plate
- spherical plastic beads / marbles / ball bearings / glass beads (e.g., <https://www.amazon.fr/1500Pcs-Couleurs-Multicolore-Fabrication-Bracelet/dp/B09MJZMFSZ>)
- aluminum tart trays (approx. 8 cm in diameter; upside-down beer cans also work, as do ashtrays)
- aluminium foil
- Lighter

Assembly

1. Place beads in a frisbee.
2. Place the trash can on top of the beads.
3. Test that trash can be spun smoothly and freely.
4. Pour a small quantity of each salt into different tart trays (approx. half a teaspoon. Less can work if you're trying to save materials, more will make it easier to have coloured flame.)
5. Pour a small quantity of ethanol in each tart tray (approx. 2 tablespoons)
6. Place aluminium foil in the bottom of the trash can.
7. Arrange tart trays symmetrically on top of the aluminium foil and test that they stay in place while spinning.
8. Light it on fire using a long lighter.
9. Once flames grow large (about 20 cm high, depending on size of tart trays and amount of ethanol), gently spin the trash bin. The flames should spin around and grow taller, forming a fire tornado!
10. As the ethanol heats up and continues to evaporate, some ions from the salt will make it into the flame and start emitting spectral colours of the cations.

OPTIONAL - Add extra ethanol to taste (this can be dangerous, so only do as much as you're comfortable with.) The goal of this is to facilitate lighting all trays without a long lighter, and to heat the ethanol-salt mixture to increase evaporation and make bigger and more colourful flames.

CAREFUL! But, this kind of starts off with a bit of a fireball, so be careful. Once flames die down a bit, colours should start to appear. Once the flames are at a manageable level, slowly spin the trash can. This should cause flames to increase in height 2-3 times and sort of wrap around each other.

What's Going On?

Elements will have typical spectral colours as a result of their electron transitions. In some cases, metal ions can emit their spectral colours when excited with the heat of a flame. This forms the basis of the "flame test", a common high-school practical for identifying ions of different elements.

Here, boric acid and two chloride salts are used. Very many other salts can be used, but these are suggested both because they are cheap and easy to find, fairly safe to use, and work pretty well.

Ethanol is recommended because it is safer and cheaper than methanol, however, if you're comfortable with using methanol it works better for two main reasons:

- most salts (including those recommended) are significantly more soluble in methanol than ethanol, and thus more easily carried into the flame
- methanol will have a colourless flame (and burn slightly more aggressively - if using methanol, do not add excess to start with a fireball - this becomes completely unnecessary and even dangerous)

The fire tornado is a popular demonstration involving angular momentum. In this case, a flame is placed inside of a spinning wire trash can. As air is drawn in towards the flame, the wire bin imparts a sideways momentum to the air. As the air continues inwards, angular momentum is conserved, which results in an acceleration of the air as it nears the centre. This gentle blows on the flames, causing them to rise significantly higher.

Troubleshooting

- **No colours appearing:** With ethanol, it may be slow for the flames to take on their spectral colour, and this may be drowned out by the yellow-orange flame. Increased concentration, temperature, and water concentration can all help, which is why the colours will be most visible near the end of the flame's life. (Ethanol evaporates faster than the salts or water. This increases the concentration both of water and of the salts, and temperature continues to rise.) This situation is accelerated by adding excess ethanol around the burners to preheat the mixtures and increase evaporation.

Additional tips and tricks

- Use whatever rotating reference frame is easy and stable for you. I use beads in a frisbee because it is lightweight, easy to travel with and cheap. At schools/venues with an old vinyl record player, this works great (maybe a little too fast, but speed can be controlled by gently braking with hands).
- An alternative approach replaces the spinning trash can with two stationary half-tubes of transparent plastic. This can work well, but care should be taken to choose a size and shape

such that the plastic won't have problems with the heat of the flame. (In my experience, empty soda and water bottles can work, but they tend to melt too easily to be worth using, except as a last resort.)

- Other salts can be used, but these are cheap and easy to find, and give three fairly distinct colours. They are also all white powders, which fits well with the storyline of "seeing the invisible" - under normal circumstances, we can't easily distinguish between them, but with the magic of fire, we can!
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Links

- David Haller showing me coloured flame tornado: <https://youtu.be/TsserR-xohY>

7. Human Photomultiplier

Inspiration

Pol Landman - Explorium, Barcelona, Spain - brainstorming before ProNRG Fest in Kazakhstan when materials for Anja's domino photomultiplier didn't come through

Scientific Concepts

Photomultiplication
Detecting weak signals
Photoelectric effect

Materials

Enthusiastic Audience (honestly, don't bother with a bad audience - this one won't work well.)

"Assembly"

This experiment is more about how you explain to the audience than about anything you prepare behind the scenes, so "Assembly" is just a copy-paste of the script from "Particle Detectives"

First, everyone needs to think of a number between 1 and 10. (Decide range to be roughly $\frac{1}{4}$ of audience size - most people won't admit when their number is called. If they are really enthusiastic, you can use animal noises, rather than numbers, but people tend to be a lot more shy for this...)

Second, I will call out a number. If I call your number, repeat your number five times. For example, if your number is 7 and I call seven, then you should say "seven, seven, seven, seven, seven". So far so good? Okay, let's test it so far. I'll call number "....".

(Some audience members should start repeating their number. If this doesn't happen, try other numbers. If it takes more numbers than it should, joke about faulty detector components.)

Notice that we were kind of able to detect the number, but it was kind of hard to hear and notice. We need a photomultiplier. That's the last step. It's also the hardest one, so please listen carefully.

1. Step three - if someone next to you, or in front or behind starts to say a number, you also need to start repeating that number. Then everyone in front, behind and next to you needs to start repeating the number, and so on and so on.

(Depending on your audience, give explicit examples, pointing to people in the audience to explain. It's surprising how poorly this can be understood if it's not explained very clearly.)

2. Ready? Let's give it a try! The number is "...."!

(It will be slow to start, and to propagate, but you should get a whole section of the room repeating the number.)

We could detect that a lot easier now that it was multiplied throughout the audience!
Congratulations, you've just become a human photomultiplier!

What's Going On?

A photomultiplier is used to multiply the electrical signal to detect a single photo (or small number of photons) which could be released by a single particle to be detected.

The photoelectric effect explains how one photon can provide energy for an electron to leave its atom. This can account for a one-electron signal from a single photon.

However, by using charge plates, an electron can be emitted with sufficient energy to emit two electrons from the next plate. By repeating, we can multiply from two to four electrons, to eight, sixteen, and so on.

Troubleshooting

- Audience is shy / unenthusiastic: This activity can work really well, but don't overestimate the enthusiasm of your audience. If the audience is not responding well before, skip this activity.

Tips and Tricks

- Choose a number which is small compared to your audience size, and even smaller if you expect sub-optimal enthusiasm.
- Make the instructions excessively clear - repeat step 2 and 3 more than reasonable. If performing to an audience with weak to intermediate comprehension of the language you present in, consider translating the instructions for added clarity. (If already translated, discuss this activity with the translator ahead of time, to make sure they understand the activity clearly and how to explain it as clearly as possible.)
- With a really good audience, it can be fun to have them choose animal noises to repeat when their number is called. (But only do this with a particularly good audience, as people tend to be even more shy to make animal noises.)

8. Timing for Applause!

Inspiration

Anja Kranjc Horvat - Seeing the Invisible

Scientific Concepts

Timing in LHC detectors
Human reaction time

Materials

- Two coloured lights (ex. RGB light used for "Coloured Fluorescence"; *Alternatively you can use a timed powerpoint of solid colours.*)

Assembly

This activity is to demonstrate the limitations of using human reaction time to observe/detect a phenomenon. We'll use the simple, quick action-reaction of clapping when you see a coloured light demonstrate how quickly this can be repeated.

1. Divide the audience into two halves and assign each to one colour of light. (ex. Right half - blue, left half - red)
2. Give the instruction for each half of the audience to clap once when they see their colour of light. Start slow and easy, with a second or two between each flash, alternating randomly between the two colours of light.
3. As the audience gets more comfortable, gradually increase speed, and explain the challenge is to find the quickest possible detection time for the audience to clap when shown a coloured light.
4. Continue increasing speed until you are showing the different colours of light with comically fast speed and it would be impossible for the audience to react in unison. Before long this will generate into applause, at which point you can take a bow, thank the audience and conclude the show!

What's Going On?

Human reaction time is typically on the order of 0.1 to 0.2 s, depending on the phenomenon being observed and the reaction. Clapping in unison in response to a coloured light should be relatively easy for speeds significantly slower than this. As speed is increased to near this range, it should be possible (but difficult) to keep up and still clap more-or-less in unison. For faster speeds this becomes impossible, and audience clapping will become more and more random, transitioning to applause.

Tips and Tricks

The colours of the lights can either be pre-programmed (i.e., in a powerpoint) or the presenter can switch them manually. Either can work; however, the latter gives the performer more control and allows them to play with the audience and adapt the activity depending on how the audience progresses through it.